

First record of *Coryssomerus capucinus* (Beck, 1817) (Coleoptera, Curculionidae) from Novosibirskaya Oblast, Western Siberia

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Academic editor: R. Yakovlev | Received 8 September 2023 | Accepted 31 October 2023 | Published 9 November 2023

<http://zoobank.org/C3E61726-A7E0-4F38-99B8-706A8C21EDA0>

Citation: Legalov AA (2023) First record of *Coryssomerus capucinus* (Beck, 1817) (Coleoptera, Curculionidae) from Novosibirskaya Oblast, Western Siberia. Acta Biologica Sibirica 9: 915–920. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10075914>

Abstract

The first record of *Coryssomerus capucinus* (Beck, 1817) (Curculionidae: Conoderinae: Conoderitae: Coryssomerini) from Novosibirskaya Oblast is given. The distribution map in Siberia, illustrations and redescription of this species are presented. It is the first record from Novosibirskaya Oblast and the easternmost finding of *C. capucinus*.

Keywords

Curculionoidea, Conoderinae, Coryssomerini, weevil, fauna, new finding, Siberia

Introduction

The tribe Coryssomerini is a diverse group of 25 genera distributed predominantly in the Afrotropical and Oriental regions (Alonso-Zarazaga and Lyal 1999). Two genera, *Coryssomerus* Schoenherr, 1825 and *Euryommatus* Roger, 1857, live in the Palearctic and the Oriental genus *Metialma* Pascoe, 1871 reaches to the north of the south of the Far East (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017; Legalov 2020). The genus *Coryssomerus* includes three species (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017). Two Corys-

somerini species were recorded in Siberia (Legalov 2020). The easternmost find of *Coryssomerus capucinus* (Beck, 1817) was Tyumen region (Bukhkalov 2011).

It is the first record of this species from Novosibirskaya Oblast and the easternmost finding of *C. capucinus*.

Materials and methods

Studied specimen is kept in the ISEA – Institute of Systematics and Ecology of Animals (Russia: Novosibirsk).

Photographs, descriptions and body measuring were performed using a Zeiss Stemi 2000-C dissecting stereomicroscope.

The terminology of weevil body is according to Lawrence et al. (2010). The systematics of studied taxa are based on Alonso-Zarazaga et al. (2017) and Legalov (2018).

Result

Superfamily Curculionoidea Latreille, 1802

Family Curculionidae Latreille, 1802

Subfamily Conoderinae Schoenherr, 1833

Supertribe Conoderitae Schoenherr, 1833

Tribe Coryssomerini Thomson, 1859

Genus *Coryssomerus* Schoenherr, 1825

Coryssomerus capucinus (Beck, 1817)

Figs 1–2

Material examined. RUSSIA 1 female (ISEA), Novosibirskaya Oblast, Toguchinskii District, 4 km W of Stepnogutovo, Tas'ma River, steppe, 54.85159° N, 84.89320° E, 186 m, 10–21.V.2022, A.A. Gurina & R.Yu. Dudko.

Description. Female. Body black, covered with white, quite narrow, appressed scales. Antennae, femora, tibiae and tarsi yellow-brown. Rostrum long, cylindrical, curved, 1.3 times as long as pronotum, 6.3 times as long as wide, and finely punctate. Forehead narrow, about 0.3 times as narrow as rostrum base width, flat, densely punctate. Eyes large, rounded, weakly protruding from contour of head, finely faceted. Vertex densely punctate. Temples short, about 0.5 times as long as eye. Antennae geniculate, quite long, inserted in middle of rostrum. Antennomere 1 elongate-trapezoidal, weakly curved in apical one third, about 4.7 times as long as wide at apex, not reaching eye. Funicle 7-segmented. Antennomeres 2 and 3 long-

conical. Antennomere 2 2.4 times as long as wide, 0.4 times as long as and 0.8 times as narrow as antennomere 1. Antennomere 3 about 2.0 times as long as wide at apex, about 0.8 times as long as and slightly narrower than antennomere 2. Antennomeres 4-6 conical. Antennomere 4 about 1.3 times as long as wide at apex, about 0.6 times as long as and 0.9 times as narrow as antennomere 4. Antennomere 5 equal in length and width, 0.8 times as long as wide, equal in wide to antennomere 4. Antennomere 6 equal to antennomere 5. Antennomeres 7 and 8 wide-conical. Antennomere 7 0.6 times as long as wide at apex, about 0.8 times as long as and about 1.3 times as wide as antennomere 6. Antennomere 8 0.5 times as long as wide at apex, equal in length and 1.2 times as wide as antennomere 7. Club compact, 1.8 times as long as wide in middle, 0.6 times as long as antennomeres 2-8 combined. Antennomere 9 1.7 times as long as wide at apex, 4.0 times as long as and about 1.2 times as wide as antennomere 8. Antennomere 10 1.5 times as long as wide at apex, equal on length and slightly wider than antennomere 9. Antennomere 11 1.4 times as long as wide at apex, lightly shorter and 0.9 times as narrow as antennomere 10. Pronotum companiform, 1.2 times as long as wide at apex, about 0.7 times as long as wide in middle and about 0.8 times as long as wide at base. Base distinctly biconcave. Disc convex, densely, coarsely punctate, with weak medial longitudinal carina. Distance between punctures smaller than puncture diameter. Pronotal constriction distinct. Sides of pronotum convex medially. Scutellum convex, slightly wider than its length, punctate. Elytra quite wide, 1.2 times as long as base width, 1.3 times as long as wide in middle, 1.6 times as long as wide in apical quarter, 2.2 times as long as wide as pronotum. Humeri convex. Striae regular scales. Interstriae wide, flattened. Apices of elytra rounded separately. Prosternum without postocular lobes and rostral channel. Precoxal portion of prosternum 0.8 times as long as procoxal length. Postcoxal portion of prosternum about 0.2 times as long as procoxal length. Mesepimeron enlarged, visible between bases of prosternum, elytra, covered with wide scales. Metacoxal cavities dilated, separated by apex of ventrite 2. Metaventrite about 2.3 times as long as metacoxa. Abdomen convex, punctate. Ventrite 1 1.9 times as long as metacoxal length. Ventrite 2 0.8 times as long as ventrite 1. Ventrites 3 and 4 equal in length, short. Ventrite 3 0.5 times as long as ventrite 2. Ventrite 4 slightly longer than ventrite 3. Ventrite 5 2.1 times as long as ventrite 4. Pygidium exposed. Legs long. Femora clavate, punctate, with large tooth. Tibiae weakly curved, weakly flattened, uncinata. Tarsi long, with pulvilli on underside. Tarsomeres 1 and 2 long-conical. Tarsomere 3 bilobed. Tarsomere 5 elongate. Claws large, free, without teeth. Body length: 3.0 mm. Rostrum length: 0.9 mm.

Remarks. This species develops on *Achillca*, *Anthemis*, *Chrysanthemum*, *Leucanthemum*, *Matricaria*, *Tanacetum* and *Tripleurospermum* (Asteraceae) (Dieckmann 1972; Rheinheimer and Hassler 2010).

Distribution. Europe, Caucasus, Western Siberia (Fig. 3).

Figure 1. *Coryssomerus capucinus* from Novosibirskaya Oblast, female, dorsal view. Scale bar 0.5 mm.

Figure 2. *Coryssomerus capucinus* from Novosibirskaya Oblast, female, lateral view. Scale bar 0.5 mm.

Figure 3. Distribution of *Coryssomerus capucinus* in Siberia.

Acknowledgements

The author thanks A.A. Gurina and R.Yu. Dudko (Novosibirsk) who collected this species.

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